

Recommended citation: Buskes, G., & Shnai, I. (2020). Evaluating the Outcomes of a Flipped Classroom. In van der Veen, J., van Hattum-Janssen, N., Järvinen, H.-M., de Laet, T., & ten Dam, I. (Eds.), *Engaging Engineering Education. SEFI 48th Annual Conference* (pp. 691-700). European Society for Engineering Education (SEFI), Enschede, The Netherlands. DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.14654027.

EVALUATING THE OUTCOMES OF A FLIPPED CLASSROOM

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Conference Key Areas: *E-learning, blended learning*

Keywords: *flipped classroom, engagement, online, blended*

ABSTRACT

In a prior paper, the authors described the planning, design and implementation of a flipped classroom for an undergraduate, third-year electrical engineering subject. The structured ADDIE (Analysis Design Development Implementation Evaluation) model was used to develop the online materials, in the form of short video lectures, and the in-class teaching and learning activities. A formal resource effectiveness analysis justified the economic viability of flipping lectures with video material, however effects of the flipped classroom on student engagement and student learning were not analysed.

This study builds upon the previous work, using data obtained during the semester to analyse how students engaged with the flipped classroom and to determine whether student learning was affected through their exposure to it. Quantitative data such as video viewing statistics, quiz responses and discussion board posts were gathered to give an insight into students' use of the content and interaction with the chosen video-hosting platform, while qualitative data from surveys and focus groups were used to further explore students' attitudes and engagement with the flipped classroom concept and its perceived effect on their learning.

The data demonstrated a marked improvement across several engagement factors, which was further backed by formal subject evaluations. Importantly, students perceived their own learning to have become more independent. The outcomes on student learning, in terms of subject academic results, showed a statistically significant shift of grades at both the upper and lower ends of the spectrum, highlighting the potential of the flipped classroom to engage a wide spectrum of students.

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1 INTRODUCTION

“Multimedia environments” include online instructional presentations, interactive lessons, e-courses, simulation games, slideshows and even media-rich text books. The effectiveness of such technologies and how they are implemented varies significantly [1]. A *flipped classroom* integrates different multimedia environments, where often online modules [2] video elements [3] and fully online environments are integrated. Core elements for the flipped classroom, according to most the common definition by practitioners, are pre-class online videos and quizzes and in-class activities and discussions [4].

The primary motivation for implementing a flipped classroom is to bring the effectiveness of active learning to the classroom by shifting the onus onto students to study the relevant material, which would ordinarily be covered in lectures, at home. The focus of in-class sessions then moves away from basic information transfer to helping students assimilate material and better develop more complex skills.

Flipped classroom researchers and practitioners note higher levels of student engagement [3, 5]. The flexibility and asynchronous nature of online videos means that students can prepare at their own pace [5] and have the useful ability to repeatedly review [6].

Transitioning to a flipped classroom releases time for more constructive learning and scaffolding in the class [3, 6]. The ability to increase the amount of active learning in-class activities and problem solving exercises permits employing higher order cognitive skills rather than basic information transfer. In addition, it allows creating more scalable and flexible learning environments, particularly for offering the subject at more regular intervals.

This research is an extension of a previous study where an Electrical Engineering subject for third-year Bachelor students was transitioned to a flipped classroom using the Flipped Classroom Design Approach [7]. A cost-effectiveness analysis of the flipped classroom implementation was performed and it was found that the resources required for the video development pay off within 1.6-6.6 years, depending on the frequency of use of the materials. This paper presents quantitative results of the flipped classroom transition in terms of its impact on student engagement, learning outcomes, and self-perception of their learning.

2 METHODOLOGY

To determine the effect of the transition to a flipped classroom for the students, two main factors were considered - their *engagement* with the subject, learning materials and teaching and learning activities, and their *learning outcomes*, measured through their subject academic results and self-perception of learning.

2.1 Measuring student engagement in the subject

The flipped classroom model that was implemented for the subject contained both synchronous (in-class) and asynchronous (online) learning opportunities for the students. Short, online video lectures were the main vehicle for basic information transfer and exposure to new concepts and could be watched at any time, with no requirements placed on having to watch them. All students were enrolled in an external video hosting platform, Edpuzzle, and could watch videos that covered the relevant theoretical material for the upcoming week of in-class teaching and learning activities. Some videos had quiz questions embedded at regular intervals that tested students' conceptual understanding and was used to tailor the in-class activities through just-in-time teaching. Data were gathered on the viewing habits of the students including which videos each student watched and how much of each video they watched.

An additional measure of students' asynchronous engagement came through monitoring the amount of online discussion board posts and the number of unique contributing users. This data could be easily compared to previous years' data to determine if there was any significant difference.

The synchronous, in-class learning sessions focused on drawing together the basic knowledge imparted by the online videos into activities that relied on higher order cognitive skills such as application, synthesis and evaluation. As there was no mechanism for capturing lecture attendance, and no prior statistics to compare to, the level of in-class engagement would be estimated using anecdotal evidence from the subject lecturer and via end-of-semester student surveys about students' perceived level of engagement, particularly with respect to their other subjects.

2.2 Measuring learning outcomes

The effect of the flipped classroom on student learning outcomes was assessed in three ways – via subject academic results, self-reported by students on the university's formal end of semester instrument for assessing teaching and learning in a subject, the Subject Experience Survey (SES), and self-reported by students via an optional end of semester student survey focusing on their experience of the flipped classroom. The SES, with its set of standard questions, is used as a benchmark to compare different subjects and could be compared to previous years' data. A focus group was also formed to get more detailed feedback on the flipped classroom at the end of the semester.

3 RESULTS

3.1 Student engagement

Of the 13 videos that were produced, 91 out of 129 students watched at least part of one of the online video lectures. Figure 1 shows the viewing rate of each video as a

proportion of those that watched one or more video. It can be seen that videos 1 and 2, which were on introductory content that had been previously covered in prerequisite subjects, were the most popular and may have served as revision for students. Videos 5-7 largely contained content that was indirectly assessed in the mid-semester test, which likely increased their viewing percentage.

Fig. 1. Viewing rate of each video as a proportion of those that watched one or more video.

Figure 2 shows the frequency of the number of videos watched by students over the semester. Note that there were no students who watched 10 or 11 videos.

Fig. 2. Frequency of the number of online videos watched by students over the semester

There is a gradual decrease in the frequency of videos watched, except for a spike representing those that watched all 13 of the videos. Note that this spike is equal to

or greater than each of the amounts between 3 and 12 and could indicate students who were deeply engaged and therefore desired to consume all of the videos.

The reasons that students gave for not watching more videos are shown in Table 1, which gives the lack of assessment as the number one reason. Note that multiple reasons could be selected for this question. It is interesting to note that not having enough time was the second highest reason and this was highly correlated ($R^2 = 0.82$) to having no assessment attached to the videos, reinforcing the concept that assessment drives student participation through prioritising their time.

Table 1. Main reason(s) for not watching more video lectures (N = 64)

Reason	Responses
There was no assessment attached to the videos	38
I didn't have time	32
The videos were not available early enough before the classes	19
I couldn't access the Edpuzzle system	12
I forgot about them	12
I didn't attend the problem-solving lectures	9
I didn't think they would suit my learning style	6

The subject provides detailed course notes in addition to the online video lecture content which may have precluded some students from referring to the videos. Furthermore, some students commented that they forgot their login for the Edpuzzle system and were reluctant to ask the subject lecturer to reset it for them.

Figure 3 gives further detail on the average viewing percentage versus the number of videos that a student watched via a box plot. The average viewing percentage is the average amount of time that a student watched the particular videos out of their total running time. It is clear that of those students that watched only one video, the average viewing time was low, at 20%. After watching one video, the average viewing for all others is above 65%, which indicates that if students progress beyond watching the first video, they are likely to watch more of the rest of the videos. There is also a high amount of variance in average viewing for the first two videos, which may be representative of the fact that they contained revision of previous material. In this case, some students would need little revision and would not watch much of the video, while others may require more.

Fig. 3. Average viewing percentage versus the number of online videos watched by students

The videos were designed to be watched before the in-class lecture sessions. Students were asked when they watched the majority of the videos and the breakdown of responses is given in Table 2. Most students watched the videos before the lecture (49%), with less than half as much watching shortly after (20%). As discussed in [7], some of the videos were released later than expected which may have caused a high number of students watching just before the lecture.

Table 2. Timeframe when students watched the majority of the online videos (N = 64)

Just before the lecture	38%
A day before the lecture	11%
Just after the lecture	20%
Sometime after the lecture	14%
During the exam study period for revision	17%

3.2 Effect on student learning

Students were surveyed at the end of semester and specifically asked about the effect of the lectures on their learning and their length, level of difficulty and format. Responses were via a 7-point Likert scale, ranging from “Strongly Disagree” to “Strongly Agree”. The results are given in Table 3.

Table 3. Student survey results on video lectures (N = 64)

Statement	Mean	Std Dev
The videos assisted me in learning the course material	6.4	0.68
The videos improved my understanding of the course material	5.8	0.77
The videos allowed me to better prepare for classes	6.2	1.04
Watching the videos increased my in-class participation	6.0	1.19
The videos helped maintain my interest in the course	5.2	0.83
The videos were of an appropriate length	6.0	0.69
The videos were of an appropriate level of difficulty	6.1	0.83
The videos were in an appropriate format (presenter on-screen, slides in background)	6.0	0.73

While the students overall agreed that the videos helped their in-class participation, the results were bi-modal and thus had the greatest standard deviation. This may be due to a proportion of the students not viewing the videos before the lecture class, as evidenced in Table 2. The lowest scoring statement, “the videos helped maintain my interest in the course”, while still positive, was not as strong as the video assisting in learning or improving understanding.

Students largely agreed that the format of the videos, with a green screen projecting slides and view of the presenter, was an appropriate format for the subject. This was backed up by a student focus group that looked at several options for the format of the videos that included the one used in the subject, with just a voice over slides and one with a reduced view of the presenter over the slides.

The learning management system for the subject has an in-built discussion board to facilitate asynchronous student questions and answers about the subject material. In the previous three years, there had been an average of just over 70 posts for the semester, with on average 16 unique users contributing in the form of questions or answering other student’s questions. With the flipped classroom implementation, this number increased to 175 posts for the semester, with 36 unique users contributing. There is no assessment linked to posting on the discussion board and no special emphasis was placed on it during semester.

The university’s formal instrument for assessing teaching and learning in a subject, the Subject Experience Survey, indicated statistically significant improvement in terms of learning resources, general teaching, and learning of new approaches and skills over the previous year’s version, shown in Table 4.

Table 4. Subject Experience Survey results (5-point Likert scale)

Statement	2018 (N=72)	2019 (N=76)
Overall, this subject has been supported by useful learning resources	4.4	4.6
Overall, this subject has been well-taught	4.5	4.6
Focusing on my own learning in this subject, I learnt new ideas, approaches and/or skills	4.3	4.5

Final subject academic results are presented in Table 5, where entries marked with an asterisk denote statistically significant differences from the year before. The shift of grades at both the upper and lower ends of the spectrum, highlights the potential of the flipped classroom to engage a wide spectrum of students, not just high or low performing ones.

Table 5. Final subject results (H1 : >80%, H2 : 70-79%, H3 : 65%-69%, P : 50%-64%, N : <50%)

Grade	2018	2019
H1	22%	28%*
H2	27%	28%
H3	18%	15%
P	20%	10%*
N	15%	18%

4 DISCUSSION

The results of the study generally support the findings in the literature that flipped classrooms can improve student engagement, usually indicated by a high rate of video views. The proportion of students that did not watch one video in this case (38/129 = 29.5%) might be considered high at face value, however this could have been affected by a number of factors. The flipped classroom was a new experience for most students and the fact that there was no assessment linked to watching the videos may have influenced student behaviour. Assessment is a key driver of participation and it is common for there to be a proportion of students who do not participate in any non-assessed teaching and learning activities. It is envisaged that in the future a small amount of assessment will be attached to the videos to observe if more students watch the videos and in a timely fashion. Delays with the publishing some of the videos may have also decreased the videos' relevance to students.

It is evident from the data in Table 3 that students made a distinction between "learning" and "understanding" when it came to the online video lectures. This could be due to students associating "learning" with observing something new for the first time and "understanding" representing a deeper form of learning, which is only achieved through continued exposure and practice.

The improvement in student final results for the subject over the previous year was a clear indicator that the flipped classroom has had a positive effect on student learning outcomes. It would have been revealing to correlate the student academic results and video-watching data with the surveys, however this was not possible due to the anonymity of the surveys. In future, ethics clearance will be sought to make the survey responses identifiable in order to better understand the relationship between student academic performance and engagement with the flipped classroom teaching and learning activities

The level of in-class engagement was difficult to gauge as there is no formal instrument for such a measure at the university and therefore no available historical data. Anecdotally, the quantity and quality of student engagement was distinctly improved over previous iterations of the subject. Students were reported to be much better prepared and more willing to challenge in-class activities with advanced questions.

5 CONCLUSION

Digitalisation embraces different sectors of our life, including education. The rapid development of technologies adaptable for education give teachers the opportunity to rethink their teaching approaches. This study focused on a subject transformation to a flipped classroom that resulted in high student engagement, as measured by video views, positive impact on student satisfaction and a strong effect on academic results.

The diversity of times when the videos were accessed as learning resources underlines the flexibility of flipped classroom and the statistically significant shift of grades at both the upper and lower ends of the spectrum highlighted the potential of the flipped classroom to engage a wide spectrum of students. Such results show a great potential for successful flipped classroom implementation given a structured and well-planned approach.

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